

Training Report

Internship Report

Submitted to the Life Sine Lab

in partial fulfillment of requirements for the award of training

Internship

in

Clinical Pathology

by

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DEPARTMENT OF PATHOLOGY

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DECLARATION

I Md. Sanaul Haque Shanto hereby declare that the **Training Report**, submitted for partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of internship of Life Sine Lab, Medical Road, Sipaipara, Rajpara is a bonafide work done by me under supervision of Khandker Md. Faisal Alam , Md. Ismail Hossain, and Nadeem Hossain

This submission represents my ideas in my own words and where ideas or words of others have been included, I have adequately and accurately cited and referenced the original sources.

I also declare that I have adhered to ethics of academic honesty and integrity and have not misrepresented or fabricated any data or idea or fact or source in my submission. I understand that any violation of the above will be a cause for disciplinary action by the institute and/or the University and can also evoke penal action from the sources which have thus not been properly cited or from whom proper permission has not been obtained. This report has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma or similar title of any other University.

Rajshahi
9-10-2022

Md. Sanaul Haque Shanto

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I take this opportunity to express my deepest sense of gratitude and sincere thanks to everyone who helped me to complete this work successfully. I express my sincere thanks to **Md. Ismail Hossain**, Head of Clinical Technologist, Clinical Pathology, Life Sine Laboratory Rajshahi for providing me with all the necessary facilities and support.

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Finally I thank my family, and friends who contributed to the successful fulfilment of this training work.

Md. Sanaul Haque Shanto

ABBREVIATION

Table 1: ABBREVIATION

Sl. No	Word	Full Meaning
1	ESR	Erythrocyte sedimentation rate
2	Hb	Hemoglobin
3	WBC	White blood cell
4	RBC	Red blood cells
5	Het	Hematocrit
6	BUN	Blood urea nitrogen
7	HIV	Human immune deficiency virus
8	RFT	Renal function test
9	LFT	Liver function test
10	KFT	Kidney function test
11	ASO	Anti Streptolysin-O
12	VDRL	Venereal disease research laboratory
13	WIDAL	Widely investigated disease assay laboratory
14	SGOT	Serum Glutamate Oxaloacetate Transaminase
15	SGPT	Serum glutamate Pyruvate Transaminase
16	ALP	Alkaline Phosphatase
17	G6PD	Glucose 6 peroxidase
18	CBC	Complete blood counts
19	mm	Millimeter
20	IU	International Unit
21	L	Low value
22	H	High value

Summary Of Training Report

This report describes a brief description of the work that has been carried out by me in the laboratory during training at **Life Sine Lab**. I have been working in laboratory during my training period from 1 August 2022 to 30 of September 2022. There were 7 department where I have worked and these department where Clinical pathology, CLIA, Biochemistry, Hematology. Serology. Microbiology, and Histopathology.

In **Clinical Pathology** I have learn how to operate (**Micro Lab RX-50V**) a semi-automated urine chemistry analyzer instrument which gives numbers of the tests Glucose, Bilirubin Ketone, Protein, Urobilinogen, Nitrite, Leukocytes, colure of the urine and pH etc. I have also examined stool slides and semen where I observed some human parasites and abnormal immotile sperms.

In **CLIA (CHEMILUMINESENCE)** in this section I have gained the knowledge of how to operate the instrument (**Thermo MULTISKAN EX Cubic Spline V2.2**) and conduct hormones test like T3, T4, and TSH. The machine is fully automated only insert the required amount of serum samples, reagents, and after 3 times of water-bath I can get the result of the test.

In **Biochemistry** in section was examine with plasma or serum and specific reagents at slide in **Lab Rotator LRA700** which give the result of Glucose, Uric acid, Cholesterol and Triglyceride.

In **Hematology** I have learned how to operate **Mythic 22** machine (CBC LH750, ESR analyzer, Coagulation profile test). The test which conduct in this machines are RBC, WBC, Platelets and clotting factors.

In **Serology** there was most of work done by manually but most of I have used readymade kit which provided by Manufacturer Company. These test were WIDAL, ASO, VDRL and free testosterone.

In **Microbiology** I have learned about staining, culture of blood, body fluids and there was (**Olympus CX23 Microscope + Spectrometer + 5 million Pixels+0.5X**)

which was microscope and measure the sensitivity of antibiotics and presence of different bacteria. I have mentioned in this report.

This is the last section where I have worked it was **Histopathology** where I did staining and section cutting of various tissues. In this section I examined the tissue and body fluid for the presence of cancer in the body.

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Chapter 1

Clinical Pathology

Introduction:

It is a medical specialty that is concerned with the diagnosis of disease based on the laboratory analysis of bodily fluids, such as **urine, semen, and stool**.

Types of sample:

1. Urine
2. Stool
3. Semen

Name of Instruments and Equipment

(a) Micro Lab RX-50V

1.1 Urine

Principles:

The reaction of Siemens Multistix 10 SG test strips depends on color development as an indicator of the concentration of the following test reactions.

Procedure urine examination:

1. Physical Gross Examination.

2. Chemical Examination.

3. Microscopic Examination.

1.1.1 Physical Examination Of Urine Determination

Determination	Normal Finding
1. Volume of Urine	50 to 200 ml
2. Color of Urine	Pale Yellow
	White
3. Appearance of Urine	Usually clear
4. Reaction	Usually acidic PH 4.88 to 7.5
	PH more than 7.5 Alkaline Urine
5. Odor of Urine	Aromatic
6. Specific gravity of Urine	Varies from 1.003 to 1.060

Table 1.1: Determination & Normal Finding of Urine

Abnormal	Pathologic
>500 ml	Diabetes insipidus, Polyuria
<20 ml	Oliguria, Anuria
Dark yellow	Hepatic and post hepatic condition
Redish	Chyluria Hematuria
Redish	Chyluria Hematuria
Black Urine	Alkaptonuria
Dark yellow	Biliverdin present
Turbid	Presence abnormal Leukocytes.
Milky	Chyle
PH less than 4.8 More, acidic Urine	Fever, Ketosis.
	Sever Vomiting.
Fruity	Acidosis, Ketosis.
Ammonical	Cystitis.
Foul smelling	Urinary tract infection.
Low Sp. Gravity	Chronic nephritis, diabetes insipidus.
High Sp. Gravity	Diabetes insipidus fever, Acute nephritis.

Table 1.2: Abnormal & Pathologic of Urine

1.1.2 Normal ranges of physical examination

TEST	ABBREVIATION	UNITS	Normal ranges
Glucose	GLU	mg/dL	NEGATIVE
Bilirubin	BIL		NEGATIVE
Ketone	KET	mg/dL	NEGATIVE
Specific Gravity	SG		1.016-1.022
pH	pH		5.0-8.0
Protein	PRO	mg/dL	NEGATIVE
Urobilinogen	URO	E.U./dL	0.2-1.0
Nitrite	NIT		NEGATIVE
Blood	BLO		NEGATIVE
Leukocytes	LEU		NEGATIVE

Table 1.3: Normal ranges of physical examination

1.1.3 CHEMICAL EXAMINATION:

SUGAR (GLUCOSE) TEST ("BENEDICT'S QUALITATIVE TEST")

Principles:

Urine glucose reduces cupric ions present in the reagent to cuprous ion, Alkaline medium is provided to the reaction by sodium carbonate present in the reagent the original color change blue to green, yellow, orange and red A/C to concentration glucose.

Procedure glucose:

1. Take 5ml of Benedict's reagent in the test tube.
2. Add 8 drops of urine.
3. Boil for 2 minute and allow cooling under tap water.

Observation & Result:

Blueclear – Negative

Green, noppt – Trace

Greenwithppt – +

Brownwithcloudy – ++

Orange with cloudy – + + +

Red with cloudy – + + + +

Disease - Hyperglycemia, Renal glycosuria.

1.1.4 Albumin Protein:

Principle:

Sulphosalicyclic acid solution (3%) precipitates any protein in the urine specimen irrespective of the type albumin or Bence Jones. It is an anion precipitant that works by the neutralization of the protein cation.

Pathogenic: Nephritic syndrome.

1.1.5 Microscopic examination of urine

In microscopic, I examined the various cells like Pus cells, RBCs, Epithelial cells, Triple phosphate Calcium oxalate, Cholesterol and Uric acid.

ROUTINE STOOL EXAMINATION

Collection of stool specimen:

Morning sample is collected in clean dry container.

LABORATORY INVESTIGATIONS

1) Gross and physical examination by visual observation:

- Consistency
- Color
- Mucus

- Blood
- Parasites

2) Chemical Examination:

- Reaction/pH
- Occult blood

3) Microscopic examination:

- Pus cell (WBC).
- RBC.
- Macrophages.
- Starch undigested.
- Vegetable fibril.
- Entamoeba histolytica (EH).
- Giardia
- Trichomonas
- Larvae
- Ova

1.2 CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF STOOL

1.2.1 BENZIDINE TEST

- Microscopic slides
- Applicator stick
- Glacial acetic acid

- 30% H₂O₂ solution
- Benzidine powder

Specimen:

Stool

PROCEDURE:

- Take pinch of Benzidine powder in a small test tube.
- Acidify it with 2 to 3 drops of glacial acetic acid and mix well.
- Add about 1.0 ml of H₂O₂ and mix well.
- Place a small quantity of stool specimen on a clean and dry slide.
- Place one or two drops of the Benzidine, glacial acetic acid, hydrogen peroxide mixture on the stool specimen on the glass slide.
- Observe change in color.

RESULT:

- No change in color-occult blood absent.
- Color changes green to blue - occult blood present.

1.2.2 MICROSCOPIC EXAMINATION OF STOOL

Requirements:

- Glass slides
- Cover slips (22 mm)
- Normal saline
- Lugol's iodine solution
- Penicillin bulb

PROCEDURE:

Saline preparation:

- Place a drop of normal saline on a glass slide
- Take a little fecal material by using a stick and mix with a drop of normal Saline.
- Place a cover slip.

Result:

1. Cells: Pus Cells, Epithelial cells, Erythrocytes
2. Parasites
3. Crystals
4. Vegetables matter
5. Undigested ingredients.
6. Other findings (Bacteria and yeast)

Date	08/08/2022	08/08/2022
Name	xyz	xyz
Sex	Male	Male
Age	28	40
Color	Brown	Brown
Consistency	Semi Formed	Semi Formed
Odor	Foul Fecal	Foul Fecal
Mucus	Absent	Absent
Blood	Absent	Absent
WBC's	Not Detected	Not Detected
Crystals	Not Detected	Not Detected
Tesrophozoit	Not Detected	Not Detected
Cyst	Not Detected	Not Detected
Ova	Not Detected	Not Detected
Larva	Not Detected	Not Detected
Adult	Not Detected	Not Detected
Occult blood	Not Detected	Not Detected

Table 1.4: Patient Data

1.3 ROUTINE SEMEN EXAMINATION

Introduction: Semen is a gray opalescent fluid which forms at ejaculation. It consists of a suspension of spermatozoa in seminal plasma. The percentage contribution of each of the secretions that make up the seminal fluids. The various important purpose of routine semen analysis is:

- Evaluation of infertility
- Routine follow up of patients who have undergone vasectomy.
- Artificial insemination.

1.3.1 PHYSICAL EXAMINATION OF SEMEN:

Color:

Volume:

Viscosity:

It is observed by taking the specimen in a Pasteur pipette and by allowing it to pour drop by drop.

The specimen of normal viscosity can be poured drop by drop.

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF SEMEN

Determine pH by using pH paper strip and note down the observed pH.

PROCEDURE:

- Pipette 5 ml of resorcinol reagent in a test tube.
- Add 0.5 ml of semen specimen.
- Mix and place in a boiling water bath for 5 minutes.

OBSERVATION:

- No change in color, Fructose absent.
- Red colored precipitate forms within 30 seconds, Fructose present.

MICROSCOPIC EXAMINATION OF SEMEN PROCEDURE:

- The semen is dilute with diluting fluid (1:20 dilution) and mixes it well.
- Take a clean glass slide.
- Charge the solution in Neubauer chamber with cover slip.
- Examine the WBC: squares, and count the sperms.

OBSERVATION:

- Abnormally shaped head.
- Abnormally sized head (giant or minute).
- Double head.
- Vacuoles in the chromatin.
- Middle section: absent, bifurcated or swollen.
- Tail: may rudimentary, double or absent.

Normal observation: Color

- Spermatozoa head caps: Light blue.
- Nuclear posterior: Dark blue.
- Bodies and tails: Red or pink.

Size:

- Spermatozoa: 50-70 μ .
- Head: 3-6 μ × 2-3 μ .

Physical examination	Microscopic examination
a) Volume: 2.0 ml b) Color: greyish white c) pH: alkaline d) viscosity: abnormal e) Sample collection time: 12:30 pm f) Liquefaction time: 4 hr	Total sperm count: 10 million/ml Motility: Actively motile :30% Sluggish motile: 20% Normal sperm: 50% Abnormal sperm: 50%

Table 1.5: Patient semen report

Chapter 2

CHEMILUMINESCENCE (CLIA)

PRINCIPLE:

The principle is based on sandwich method of antigen-antibody reaction. Acredium Ester binds to the antibody in the presence of a specific antigen and forms a sandwich Formation (Ag-Ab-Acredium ester), as a result of chemical reaction between Ag. Ab & Acredium ester emission of light is occurred by Acredium ester, the amount of light emitted is directly proportional to the antigen present in the sample.

INSTRUMENT NAME: Thermo MULTISKAN EX Cubic Spline V2.2

PARTS OF INSTRUMENT:

- Improcess Queue
- Sample probe
- Ancillary probe
- Tip tray
- Cuvette bin
- Cuvette wheel
- Reagent rack
- Reagent probe
- Illuminometer
- Waste keeping container
- Exit Queue

(a) Thermo MULTISKAN EX Cubic Spline V2.2

2.1 NAME OF THE TEST:

- T_3 (TRI-iodothyronine)
- T_4 (Thyroxine)
- TSH (Thyroid Stimulating Hormone)

2.2 T_3 (Triiodothyronine) AND T_4 (Thyroxine):

Triiodothyronine (T_3) and Thyroxine (T_4). It is based on essential hormone produced by the Thyroid gland. Triiodothyronine (T_3) is about four times more active in its biological functions than thyroxine (T_4).

FUNCTION OF TRIIODOTHYRONINE (T_3) AND THYROXINE (T_4):

Thyroid hormones stimulate the metabolic activities.

- It increases the oxygen consumption in most of the tissues of the body.
- Effect on protein synthesis: Thyroid hormones act like steroid hormones in promoting protein synthesis.
- Influence on carbohydrate metabolism: Thyroid hormones promote intestinal absorption of glucose and its utilization.
- Effect on lipid metabolism: Lipid turnover and utilization are stimulated by thyroid hormone.

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE:

- Increase in the size of the thyroid gland is known as Goiter.
- Increase level of thyroid hormone is known as Hyperthyroidism.
- Decrease level of thyroid hormone is known as Hypothyroidism.

2.3 TSH (THYROID STIMULATING HORMONE):

TSH is a dimer (a β) glycoprotein with a molecular weight of about 30,000. The release Of TSH from anterior pituitary is controlled by feedback mechanism. The hormones of The thyroid gland (T_3 , and T_4) and thyrotrophic releasing hormone (TRH) of Hypothalamus.

FUNCTIONS:

- It is promotes the uptake of iodine (iodide pump) from the circulation by thyroid gland.
- Enhance the conversion of iodide to active iodide, a process is known as organification.
- Increase the proteolysis of thyroglobulin to release T_3 , and T_4 , into the circulation.

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE:

- Increase level of TSH: Hypopituitarism.
- Decrease level of TSH: Hypopituitarism.

Case Study 01

Patient Name:

Age/Sex: 31/M

Sample Date: 02/09/2022

Reporting Date: 02/09/2022

TEST RESULT	UNIT	NORMAL RANGE
$T_3 = 188.5(\text{H})$	$\mu\text{g/dL}$	$T_3 = 60 - 181\eta \text{ g/dL}$
$T_4 = 3.5(\text{L})$	$\mu\text{g/dL}$	$T_4 = 45-12.6\mu\text{g/dL}$
TSH=8.25(H)	$\mu\text{IU/L}$	TSH=0.35-5.5 $\mu\text{IU/L}$

Table 2.1: Unit and Normal ranges

Case Study 02

Patient Name:

Age/Sex: 35/F

Sample Date: 02/09/2022

Reporting Date: 02/09/2022

TEST RESULT	UNIT	NORMAL RANGE
$T_3 = 188.5(\text{H})$	$\eta \text{ g/dL}$	$T_3 = 60 - 181\eta \text{ g/dL}$
$T_4 = 3.5(\text{L})$	$\mu\text{g/dL}$	$T_4 = 45-12.6\mu\text{g/dL}$
TSH=8.25(H)	$\mu\text{IU/L}$	TSH=0.35-5.5 $\mu\text{IU/L}$

Table 2.2: Patient report

Chapter 3

BIOCHEMISTRY

INTRODUCTION:

Clinical Biochemistry deals with the biochemistry laboratory applications. To find out Cause of disease. The chemical constituent of various body fluid such as Blood, Urine, CSF and other body fluid like are analyzed in clinical biochemistry laboratory. The Biochemistry test are very useful to determine the severity of disease of many organ. The Clinical biochemistry tests in relation to the various clinical conditions.

1. The cause of disease
2. Screen assay diagnosis.
3. Suggested effective treatment.
4. Monitoring process of a pathological condition
5. Help in assessing response to therapy

PRINCIPLE:

The Principle of this instrument is based on Lamberts and Beers law. The optical density (O.D) is directly proportional to the concentration of solution and the thickness of the Cuvette.

Figure 3.1: Biochemistry Analyzer

3.0.1 NAME OF INSTRUMENT:

1. Plasma or Serum, Reagents, Slides, Incubator, and LRA700.

NAME OF THE TEST:

3.0.2 Glucose

- Fasting blood sugar
- Random blood sugar
- Postprandial blood sugar

3.0.3 Renal function test (RFT)

3.0.4 Liver Function Test (LFT)

- Bilirubin Direct and Total
- SGPT
- SGOT

- ALP

4.

3.1 Lipid Profile.

- Cholesterol
- Triglyceride

Principle:

UV test enzymatic reference method with hexokinase. Hexokinase catalyzes the phosphorylation of glucose to glucose-6-phosphate by ATP. Glucose + ATP → Glucose-6-phosphate + ADP. Hexokinase/Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase oxidizes glucose-6-phosphate in the presence of NADP to gluconate-6-phosphate. The rate of NADPH formation during the reaction is directly proportional to the glucose concentration and is measured photo metrically.

Procedure:

Separate the serum or plasma sample from the test tube with the help of micro pipette. Take the sample in a cuvette. Give the command to the analyzer and select the tests. Press ok. Then place the cuvette in the analyzer. Analyzer gives result automatically.

Normal ranges of glucose

Fasting	Postprandial	Random
70-150 mg/dl	70-150 mg/dl	100-150 mg/dl

Table 3.1: Normal ranges of glucose

Case Study 01

Name:

Age/sex: 41/male

Sample: Fasting plasma

Result obtained: 140 mg/dl

Interpretation: The blood glucose level in the patient is high which indicates hyperglycemia.

Case Study 02

Name:

Age/sex: 32/male

Sample: Random plasma

Result obtained: 60 mg/dl

Interpretation: The blood glucose level in the patient is low which indicates hypoglycemia.

Clinical significance

Hyperglycemia

- Diabetes mellitus
- Hyperactivity of thyroid, adrenal, pituitary gland

Hypoglycemia

- Overdose of insulin
- Hypo activity of thyroid, adrenal, or pituitary gland

3.1.1 RFT (RENAL FUNCTION TEST)

Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) Principle: Kinetic test with urease and glutamate dehydrogenase: Urea is hydrolyzed by urease to form ammonium and carbonate.

In the second reaction 2-oxoglutarate reacts with ammonium in the presence of glutamate dehydrogenase (GLDH) and the coenzyme NADH to produce L-glutamate. In this reaction two moles of NADH are oxidized to NAD for each mole of urea hydrolyzed.

The rate of decrease in the NADH concentration is directly proportional to the urea concentration in the specimen and is measured photo metrically.

Normal range: 7-10 mg/dl.

Case Study: 01

Name:

Age/sex: 21/Female

Sample: Serum

Result obtained: 6 mg/dL

Interpretation: The blood urea nitrogen level in the patient is low.

Case Study: 02

Name:

Age/sex: 34/Female

Sample: Serum

Result obtained: 26 mg/dL

Interpretation: The blood urea nitrogen level in the patient is high.

Clinical Significance

An abnormally high level of urea nitrogen in the blood is an indication of kidney function impairment or failure. Some other causes of increased values for urea nitrogen include perianal azotemia (e.g. shock), post renal azotemia, GI bleeding, and a high protein diet. Some causes of decreased values for urea nitrogen include pregnancy, severe liver insufficiency, over hydration and malnutrition.

3.1.2 LIVER FUNCTION TEST (LFT)

Introduction

Liver function tests (LFTs) are commonly used in clinical practice to screen for liver disease, monitor the progression of known disease, and monitor the effects of potentially hepatotoxic drugs. The most common LFTs include the serum aminotransferases, alkaline phosphatase, bilirubin, albumin, and prothrombin time. Aminotransferases, such as alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST), measure the concentration of intracellular hepatic enzymes that leaked into the circulation and serve as a marker of hepatocyte injury.

TOTAL BILIRUBIN Principle:

Diazotized Sulfanilic acid is formed by combining sodium nitrite and sulfanilic acid at low pH. The sample is diluted in 0.05M Hydrochloric acid. A blank reading is taken to eliminate interference from non-bilirubin pigments. Upon addition of the diazotized sulfanilic acid, the conjugate bilirubin is converted to diazo-bilirubin, a red chromophore which absorbs at 540nm.

Normal range: 0.20-1.00mg/dl.

Case Study: 01

Name:

Age/sex: 38/Male

Sample: Serum

Result obtained: 1.53 mg/dL

Interpretation: Total Bilirubin level in patient's serum is high.

Clinical Significance

High levels of bilirubin in the blood may be caused by:

- Some infections, such as an infected gallbladder.
- Some inherited diseases, such as Gilbert's syndrome, a condition that affects how the liver processes bilirubin. Although jaundice may occur in some people with

Gilbert's syndrome, the condition is not harmful.

- Diseases that cause liver damage, such as hepatitis, cirrhosis, or mononucleosis.
- Diseases that cause blockage of the bile ducts, such as gallstones or cancer of the pancreas.

3.1.3 SGPT (Serum glutamate Pyruvate Transaminase)

(Also called ALT (Alanine Transaminase))

Principle:

Alanine aminotransferase catalyzes the transamination of L-alanine to a-ketoglutarate, forming L glutamate and pyruvate. The pyruvate formed is reduced to lactate by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) with simultaneous oxidation of reduced nicotinamide-adenine dinucleotide (NADH). The change in absorbance is directly proportional to the ALT activity and is measured using a dichromatic (340, 700 nm) rate technique.

Normal range: 30-65 U/L.

Case Study

Name:

Age/sex: 21/female

Sample: serum

Result obtained: 116 U/L

Interpretation: The ALT level in patient's serum is high.

Clinical Significance

High levels of ALT may be caused by:

- Liver damage from conditions such as hepatitis or cirrhosis.

- Lead poisoning.
- Exposure to carbon tetrachloride.
- Decay of a large tumor (necrosis).

3.1.4 SGOT (Serum Glutamate Oxaloacetate Transaminase)

Also called AST (Aspartate Transaminase)

Principle:

Aspartate aminotransferase catalyzes the transamination of L-aspartate to α -Ketoglutarate, forming L-glutamate and oxaloacetate. The oxaloacetate formed is reduced to malate by malate dehydrogenase (MDH) with simultaneous oxidation of reduced nicotinamide-adenine dinucleotide (NADH). The change in absorbance with time due to the conversion of NADH to NAD is directly proportional to the AST activity and is measured using a dichromatic (340, 700 nm) rate technique.

Normal range: 15-37 U/L.

Case study: 01

Name:

Age/sex: 21/female

Sample: serum

Result obtained: 52 U/L

Interpretation: The AST level in patient's serum is high.

Clinical significance

An increase in AST levels may indicate:

- Acute hemolytic anemia
- Acute pancreatitis

- Acute renal failure.
- Liver cirrhosis
- Heart attack
- Hepatitis
- Infectious mononucleosis
- Liver cancer
- Liver necrosis

3.2 LIPID PROFILE

3.2.1 CHOLESTEROL

Principle:

Cholesterol esters are hydrolyzed by cholesterol ester hydrolase to produce free cholesterol and fatty acids. The free cholesterol produced and pre-existing one is oxidized by cholesterol oxidase to cholestenone-4-en-3-one and hydrogen peroxide. Hydrogen peroxide thus formed is used to oxidize N. N diethylaniline-4-aminoantipyrine to produce a chromosphere that absorbs at 540 nm. The absorbance due to oxidized N. N diethyl aniline- 4-amincantipyrine is directly proportional to the total cholesterol concentration and is measured using a polychromatic (452, 540,700 nm) end point technique.

Normal range: 0-200mg/dl.

Case study

Name:

Age/sex: 21/female.

Sample: serum

Result obtained: 236 mg/dl,

Interpretation: The cholesterol level in patient's serum is high.

Clinical Significance

Elevated levels of serum cholesterol are associated with atherosclerosis, nephritis, diabetes mellitus, Obstructive jaundice, Biliary cirrhosis, lipoproteinemias, and myxedema. Decreased level in cholesterol is associated with severe infection, severe anemia, and malnutrition.

TRIGLYCERIDES

Principle:

Triglycerides + water + Glycerol + ATP → Glycerol kinase Lipoprotein Lipase Glycerol-3-phosphate + oxygen + Hydrogen peroxide

Glycerol + fatty acids + Hydrogen peroxide + Aminoantipyrine → Glycerol phosphate oxidase Glycerol-3-phosphate + ADP + Quinonimine + HCL + 4-Chlorophenol + 4H₂O

The change in absorbance due to the formation of Quinonimine is directly proportional to the total amount of glycerol and its precursors in the sample and is measured using a dichromatic (510, 700 nm) endpoint technique.

Normal range: 15-1000mg/dl

Case study

Name:

Age/sex: 34/male

Sample: Serum

Result obtained: 156 mg/dl.

Interpretation: the triglycerides level in patient is high.

Clinical significance:

TG level decreases in:

- Liver disease
- Cerebral infarction,

- Hyper parathyroidism,
- Hyperthyroidism,
- Lactosuria,

TG level increases

Heart disease	Renal disease
After severe myocardial infarction Atherosclerosis, Coronary artery disease, Essential hypertension, Ischemic heart disease Malignant hypertension,	Chronic renal failure, Nephrotic syndrome, Uremia without nephrosis

Table 3.2: Various diseases

Chapter 4

HEMATOLOGY

4.0.1 HEAMATOLOGY

INTRODUCTION:

Hematology is the study of blood, blood components, and blood disorders it involves Studying the anatomy and physiology of blood cells and other cells that compressed Blood like Red blood cells White blood cells Platelets and hemoglobin.

1. Analysis of blood concentration, structure and function of the cells and their precursors In the bone marrow.
2. Analysis of chemical constituents of plasma or serum intimately, linked blood cells Structure and function.

Study of function of the platelets and proteins involved in blood coagulation.

NAME OF THE INSTRUMENT:

- Mythic 22 (For detection of Hb, Platelets and CBC)
- Roll Mixer
- Wintrobe tube

(a) Mythic 22 Hematology Analyzer

NAME OF THE TEST:

1. Complete blood Count (CBC)
2. Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR)
3. Blood grouping
4. Differential leukocyte count (DLC)
5. G-6-PD-1
6. Coagulation profile

4.1 Complete blood Count (CBC)

PRINCIPLE OF CBC ANALYSIS:

The Coulter method accurately counts and sizes cells by detecting and measuring changes in electrical resistance. When a particle (such as a cell) in a conductive liquid passes through a small aperture. Each cell suspended in a conductive liquid (diluent) acts as an insulator. As each cell goes through the aperture, it momentarily increases the resistance of the electrical path between the submerged electrodes on either side of the aperture. This causes a measurable electronic pulse. For counting, the vacuum used to pull the diluted suspension of cells through the aperture must be at a regulated volume.

PARTS OF THE INSTRUMENTS:

- Aperture Current
- External electrode.
- Sample beaker.
- Aperture
- Aperture tube.
- Blood cell suspension.

Case Study

Date	Name	Age/Sex
08/08/2022		23/M
08/08/2022		45/F

Table 4.1: Patient Data

Results

		Normal range
WBC = 3.8(L)	WBC = 3.8(L)	4-11 cumm
NE = 64.4%	NE = 64.4%	40-75%
LY = 14.9%(L)	LY = 14.9%(L)	20-45%
MO = 17.2%(H)	MO = 17.2%(H)	2-8%
EO = 2.4%	EO = 2.4%	1-4%
BA = 1.1%	BA = 1.1%	0-1%
RBC = 4.07(L)	RBC = 4.07(L)	3-5 Lakh
HGB = 12.2(L)	HGB = 12.2(L)	13-17 g/dl
HCT = 37.1(L)	HCT = 37.1(L)	42-52%
MCV = 91.1	MCV = 91.1	80-100 fl
MCH = 30.0	MCH = 30.0	27-32 Pg.
MCHC = 32.9	MCHC = 32.9	32-36%
RDW = 15.7%(H)	RDW = 15.7%(H)	11-14%

Table 4.2: Results

4.2 Erythrocyte sedimentation rate

PRINCIPLE:

The red cells form Rouleaux, The settling/sedimentation of RBC's occur at a constant rate. The individual cells also aggregates due to overcrowding, and get packed down on the bottom of the tube.

(a) ESR Analyzer

Reagents and Equipment:

1. Automated Analyzer
2. Westergren tube rack
3. Timer
4. 3.8% tri-sodium citrate
5. Test tubes

PROCEDURE:

- Take a clean dry centrifuge tube.
- Add 0.5ml of 3.8% sodium citrate.
- Add 2 ml blood sample into the tube and mix it.
- Fill the Westergren tube up to '0' mark.
- Pull the tube in vertical position on the stand.

Clinical Significance

ESR increased in:	ESR decreased in:
Chronic inflammations & infections Eg. TB	Polycythemia
Acute inflammations & infections	Sickle cell disease
Normal Pregnancy (Physiological)	Cryoglobinaemia

Table 4.3

Patient Name	Age/Sex	Result	Normal Range
	72/F	26/mm/h	Female (0-20) mm/h

Table 4.4

Case Study

4.3 ABO BLOOD GROUPING BY (Slide Method)

PRINCIPLE:

Serum of the specimen submitted is reacted with known A cells and B cells. Agglutination indicates presence of corresponding antisera in serum.

PROCEDURE:

1. Place 1 drop of anti-A and 1 drop of anti-B reagent separately on a labeled slide or tile.
2. Add 1 drop of 20% test red cell suspension to each drop of the typing antiserum (the Suspension may be prepared by adding 20 parts of red cells to 80 part of normal saline).
3. Mix the cells and reagent using a clean stick. Spread each mixture evenly on the slide over an area of 10-15 mm diameter.
4. Tilt the slide and leave the test for 2 minutes at room temperature. Then rock again and Look for agglutination.
5. Record the results.

Observation:

Figure 4.3: Blood grouping slide

4.4 GLUCOSE-6-PHOSPHATE DEHYDROGENASE (G6PD):

This test measures the amount of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) in blood. G6PD is an enzyme in the body. This test is used to evaluate and manage G6PD enzyme deficiency. This test may also be used if infection is suspected.

PRINCIPLE:

Reaction	Monoclonal Antibodies A	Monoclonal Antibodies B	Monoclonal Antibodies D	Result Blood Group
Agglutination	+	-	+	A Positive
Agglutination	+	-	-	A Negative
Agglutination	-	+	+	B Positive
Agglutination	-	+	-	B Negative
Agglutination	+	+	+	AB Positive
Agglutination	+	+	-	AB - Negative
Agglutination	-	-	+	O Positive
Agglutination	-	-	-	O Negative

Table 4.5: Blood grouping reaction

Glucose-6-Phosphate Dehydrogenase present in hemolysate acts on substrate, Glucose-6-Phosphate (G6P) and NADP which in presence of PMS decolorizes blue colored indophenol dye(DCPIP) leaving behind color only due to hemolysate. The rate of reaction being proportional to enzyme activity (G6PD) present, time required for decolorization is inversely proportional to enzyme activity in hemolysate.

KIT REAGENT

1. Lyse agent
2. Buffer
3. Inert oil

PROCEDURE:

1. Take 20ml blood in a vial
2. Put 1ml of lysing agent in it.
3. Keep it in refrigerator for 10 mins.
4. Add 5ml of buffer to the powdered detergent.
5. Add 1ml of inert oil in it
6. Mix well and incubate it for 1 hr.
7. Observe the color change.

OBSEVATION:

1. Normal subjects: 30-60 mints.
2. G-6PD deficient subject (Heterozygous male, homozygous female): 140 mints to 24 hrs.
3. G-6PD carriers (Heterozygous female): Some give result which overlap with normal males, other decolorizes between 90 mints and several hours.

Case Study

Name	Age	Sex	Result
	35	Female	Positive

4.5 COAGULATION TIME (CT)

PRINCIPLE:

Automated coagulation machines or Coagulometers measure the ability of blood to clot by performing any of several types of tests including Partial thromboplastic times, Prothrombin times (and the calculated INRs commonly used for therapeutic evaluation), Lupus anticoagulant screens, D dimer assays, and factor.

(a) COAGULATION Analyzer

4.5.1 Procedure:-

1. Take the tube
2. Scan and insert into the its position and select the test
3. Start the test
4. If reagent is not then refill it.

Normal Range of Coagulation studies

PT-11 to 16 sec & APTT-35 to 40 sec

Clinical Significance of PT:

- Prothrombin deficiency
- Vitamine deficiency
- Hemorrhagic diseases of the newborn.
- Liver disease (e.g. Akoholic hepatitis)
- Biliary obstruction

Comparative of Increasing and Decreasing value (APTT)

Increase: Hemophilia deficiency of VIII, IX, XI, V, X and XII.

Decrease: (DIC) Disseminated intravascular coagulation.

Case Study

Name	Age/Sex	Result
	41/Female	17sec PT 42sec APTT

Table 4.6: Patient Result

Chapter 5

SEROLOGY

Introduction:

Serology is the study of immune bodies in human blood. These immune bodies are the product of the defense mechanisms against disease-causing organisms in the body. The principle involved with serology is the antibody-antigen response. The antigen actually comes first, in that the antigen is the substance which "provokes the body to produce antibodies.

The tests performed in serology lab:

1. WIDAL test
2. ASO (Anti Streptolysin O)
3. VDRL (Venereal disease research laboratory)

5.1 WIDAL TEST: -

WIDAL slide test provides a simple way of qualitatively and semi-quantitatively estimating the antibodies to *S.typhi* (O & H) and *S.paratyphi* (AH & BH). It is based on the principle of direct agglutination. When the patient's serum (containing antibodies to *S.typhi* & *S.paratyphi*).

KIT CONTENT

Antigen of *S. typhi* & *S. paratyphi*.

- S. 'H'.
- S. paratyphi AHS.
- S. 'BH'.
- P +ve cont.
- Glass slide.

(a) WIDAL Test and Kits

Procedure of WIDAL test:

Take a clean glass slide-add serum 1 drop in each four circle-add a drop of all 4 antigens in each circle.1,2,3,and 4.

RESULT: If Agglutination titer if 1:80 or more is significant. An increase in titer, 4 to 5 days after the first test is suggestive if active Salmonella infection.

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE:

S. typhi, *S. paratyphi* based on their antigenic structure are classified as 'O' (somatic) and 'H' (FLAGELLAR) Antigens.

'O' antigens of various species have common antigenic components. Hence only one antigen *S. typhi* O' is used in the routine test's' antigen is species specific.

5.2 VDRL (Venereal disease research laboratory)

PRINCIPLE:

Patients suffering from syphilis produce antibodies that react with Cardiolipin antigen in a slide flocculation test, which are read using a microscope.

Procedure:-

Add 50ul serum sample at RT add 20ul antigen and shake it- mix with sticks-rotate for 4min at 150rpm. And see the agglutination.

Results interpretation:

POSITIVE REACTION: Marked and intense visible aggregates are seen. sample is reactive.

POSITIVE REACTION: Slight but definite small aggregates are seen. Serum sample weakly reactive.

NEGATIVE REACTION: The mixture remains in a smooth suspension with no visible aggregates. Serum is non-reactive.

5.3 ASO (Anti Streptolysin O)

It is a rapid latex agglutination test for the qualitative and semi- quantitative determination of anti-Streptolysin-O antibodies (ASO) in serum. In infections caused by β -hemolytic streptococci, Streptolysin-O is one of the two hemolytic exotoxins liberated from the bacteria that stimulate production of ASO antibodies in the human serum.

PRINCIPLE:

The ASO is a rapid agglutination procedure for the direct detection and semi-quantitation (on slide) of anti-Streptolysin. The antigen, a latex particles suspension coated with Streptolysin O, agglutination in the presence of specific antibodies present

in sera of patients with Streptococcal beta- hemolytic infection (Group A and C).

Figure 5.2: ASO Kits

PROCEDURE

1. Place 1 drop of serum sample on to the slide with the help of disposal serum dropper,
2. Add 1 drop of ASO- Latex Antigen to the slide
3. Mix properly with the applicator stick
4. Rotate for 2min in a rotator

5. Observe for agglutination

Case Study

Name	Age /Sex	Result	ASO	VDRL	WIDAL
	23/F	Agglutination	+ve	-ve	-ve
	21/F	Agglutination	-ve	+ve	-ve
	19/F	Agglutination	-ve	-ve	+ve

Table 5.1: Patients positive cases.

5.4 HIV Tri- dot test

Principle

HIV antigens are immobilized on a porous immunofiltration membrane. Sample and the reagent pass through the membrane and are absorbed into the underlying absorbent. As the patients sample passes through the membrane, HIV antibodies, if present, bind to the Immobilized antigens. Conjugate binds to the Fc portion of the HIV antibodies to give distinct pinkish purple Dot (s) against a white background.

Specimen requirement

Scrum Iml

Procedure

1. Add 3 drops of buffer solution to the center of the device.
2. Hold the dropper vertically and add 1 drop of patient's sample (serum or plasma).
3. Add 5 drops of buffer solution.
4. Add 2 drops of liquid conjugate directly from the conjugate vial.
5. Add 5 drops buffer solution and read the results

Result:

- Report the result positive when both line is appeared control and HIV.

Chapter 6

MICROBIOLOGY

Introduction

Clinical microbiology is the branch of medical science that deals with the study of Microorganisms that infect humans, the disease they cause, their diagnosis prevention, and Microbiology treatment.

Here microbiology department is divided into three sub departments.:

1. Bacteriology department
2. Mycology department
3. Tuberculosis department

Types of sample received in Laboratory

- Urine (mostly received)
- Sputum sample
- Blood sample
- Stool sample
- Throat swab
- Water
- FNAC smear

Instruments:

1. Bactec system
2. Microscan
3. Microscope
4. Hot air oven
5. Incubator

Procedure for culture:

Urine, Stool, Body fluid, and CSF etc...

1. Take the sample
2. Inoculate the sample into the media and keep inverted position
3. And keep all equipment in the laminar air flow plate
4. After cold keep the media into the incubator at RT for 24 hrs.
5. Incubator

Result:

-note down the result after 24 hrs. Or 48 hrs..

6.1 Microscopy:

Wet mount is prepared. Single drop of urine is taken in a clean and dry slide, put on the coverslip and observe under the microscopy.

6.1.1 BACTEC

Principle

The sample to be tested is inoculated into the vial which is entered into the BACTEC instrument for incubation and periodic reading. Each vial contains a sensor which responds to the concentration of CO₂ produced by the metabolism of microorganisms or the consumption of oxygen needed for the growth of microorganisms.

Anaerobic culture and Aerobic culture.

Procedure:

1. Introduce the blood about 5ml into the both bottle
2. Put the bottle for 24 and 48 and 72hrs
3. Red light shows the positive and negative.
4. Positive culture can take to grow on media.

STAINING

Gram staining Principle

1. Place the slide on the staining glass rods.
2. Cover the smear with crystal violet stain and leave for 1 minute.
3. Wash carefully under running tap water.
4. Flood the smear with the gram's solution and wait for one minute.
5. Drain off the iodine.
6. Decolorize the smear with alcohol-acetone water. (or rectified spirit) for 20-30 seconds (continue till purple stain just stops coming on the slide).

Acid staining Principle

1. Prepare Smear from the sputum specimen on glass slide and fix it by heating.
2. Flood slide with Carbol-fuchsin stain, heat the slide gently with a flame for 5 minutes.
3. Do not over heat the stain if necessary add carbol-fuchsin.
4. Rinse off the over stain under running tap water.
5. Decolorize with acid alcohol or 20% H₂SO₄ for about 1 minute or until no more color comes off.
6. Rinse again in running tap water.
7. Counter stain with methylene blue for 30 sec.
8. Examine under microscope with oil immersion objective.

RESULTS

Gram stain	Acid fast AF
Yeast cells: Dark purple Epithelial cells: Pale red Nuclei of pus cell: Red Gram positive bacteria: Dark purple Gram negative bacteria: Pale to dark red.	Acid fast (AF) organisms Bright red bacilli on blue background. Other organisms - Dark blue

Table 6.1: Result of various stain

Chapter 7

HISTOPATHOLOGY

Introduction

(compound of three Greek words: histos "tissue", pathos "suffering", and - logia "study of") refers to the microscopic examination of tissue in order to study the manifestations of disease.

(a) Preparation

(b) Olympus CX23 Microscope

Figure 7.1: Microscopic examination of tissue

Biopsy	FNAC	Autopsy	Amputated limbs	LBC
Utrus	Lump	From dade body	From alive person	Vaginal discharge
Placenta	Bump		Upper limb	Fluids
Slivary gland		Lower limb		
Cervical				
Kidney				

Table 7.1: Specimen of Uterus.

Types of samples:-

7.1 Histopathological Instrument and equipments:-

- Microtome
- Microtome knife
- Timer
- Hot air oven
- Forceps
- Scalpel, dissecting set
- Tissue floatation bath
- Equipment for embedding and vacuum
- Containers for holding specimens

7.1.1 Steps for the Tissue processing

1. Grossing
2. Labeling
3. Fixation
4. Dehydration
5. Clearing
6. Impregnation

7. Embedding
8. Microtomy
9. Staining
10. Microscopic observation

7.1.2 Procedure

Grossing: Tissue cuts into tissue small pieces like 3-4mm.

Labeling: Every tissue need to give an identity for Recognize.

Fixation: It prevent need to decompose give an Exp: Formalin.

from natural **Dehydration:** Water removed by different grade of Iso by propyl alcohol. 50% Alcohol It used 70%,90%,and with two 95% .

Clearing: Alcohol is removed by Xylene. It used with two changes changes 1 & IInd.

Impregnation: It remove the clearing reagent paraffin. Tissue transfer into P. Wax Ist, IInd and IIIrd changes. Temperature should be 2-3 degree more than its melting point Paraffin wax.

7.1.3 Staining of the slides:-

1. Ziehl nelson stain for acid fast bacilli(Acid fast stain)
2. PAP stain
3. Giemsa stain
4. PAS (Periodic Acid Schiff) stain

Mounting: after staining I do mounting with DPX then slide send to the histopathologist.

Observation:- senior pathologist does all examination of the slides.

Results: If we find the abnormal structure in nucleus and cytoplasm of the cells then it may report as the cancerous cases or diseases case.

7.1.4 Case Study

Specimen	Name	Age/sex	Result	Disease	Remark
Uterus endometrium		40/F	Positive for Cancer	Cancer	Malignancy of Uterine cancer

Table 7.2: Specimen of Uterus

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